

TO STUDY THE MOLECULAR DOCKING OF OMICRON VARIANT WITH SEVERAL ANTIMICROBIAL DRUGS USING AutoDock TOOLS

Shivani Sharma, Dr. Dinesh Kaushik

Department of Pharmaceutics, Hindu College of Pharmacy, Sonipat-131001, Haryana, India.

ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 07/06/2023

Available online

26/06/2023

Keywords

Omicron,
Mutations,
Molecular Docking,
Receptor,
Virus.

ABSTRACT

A new SARS-CoV-2 variant of concern (VoC) omicron was reported. The Omicron was initially discovered in Botswana and South Africa, and it is rapidly spreading throughout the world. As of December 16, 2021, it had spread to five continents. More than 30 mutations overlap with those in the alpha, beta, gamma, or delta VoCs. These deletions and mutations are known to lead to increased transmissibility, higher viral binding affinity, and higher antibody escape. Molecular docking is a technique of virtual simulation which is used to model the interaction between a small molecule and a protein at the atomic level. This technique is also used to characterize the behavior of the small molecules in the binding site of target protein. Molecular docking is a computational technique to study the interaction between a target receptor and ligand at the molecular level and allows ranking of the ligands by assessing their binding affinity towards the receptor using various scoring functions. The docking process involves two basic steps - prediction of the ligand conformation and 2nd is binding of ligand within a target active site with accuracy that's why it technique is commonly used in structure-based drug design (SBDD). Steps of molecular Docking are Protein structure preparation, the top five medications, based on their binding energy, and were chosen from a pool of 50 drugs as Dihydroergotamine, Ergotamine, Nofamostat, Methylegonovine, and Clarithromycin.

Corresponding author

Shivani Sharma

Department of Pharmaceutics,
Hindu College of Pharmacy, Sonipat-131001, Haryana, India.
shivanisharmasp@gmail.com

Please cite this article in press as **Shivani Sharma et al.** To Study the Molecular Docking of Omicron Variant with Several Antimicrobial Drugs Using Autodock Tools. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2023; 13(06).

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INTRODUCTION

The Omicron was initially discovered in Botswana and South Africa, and it is rapidly spreading throughout South Africa and the world. As of December 16, 2021, it had spread to five continents: Europe, North America, Asia, South America, Africa, and Oceania, with at least 77 nations reporting Omicron cases, including the United States, the United Kingdom, France, Germany, Australia, Japan, and China. [1].

Figure 1: Structure of Omicron.

Prompting anxiety and uncertainty in the global fight against the COVID-19 pandemic. Omicron has some deletions and more than 30 mutations, several of which (egg, 69–70del, T95I, G142D/143–145del, K417N, T478K, N501Y, N655Y, N679K, and P681H) overlap with those in the alpha, beta, gamma, or delta VoCs. These deletions and mutations are known to lead to increased transmissibility, higher viral binding affinity, and higher antibody escape. Some of the other omicron mutations with known effects confer increased transmissibility and affect binding affinity [2].

ORIGIN OFOMICRON VARIANT

A specimen taken on November 9, 2021 was the first known verified B.1.1.529 infection. After sequencing additional eight viruses, Lancet Laboratories in South Africa discovered that normal polymerase chain reaction (PCR) testing for SARS-CoV-2 failed to identify the S gene, a crucial target in many viral samples.[3,4]

Figure 2: Spreading Rate of Omicron Variant in South Africa.

The genome was too highly altered to test the missing gene. The genomes were then shared with the South African Network for Genomics Surveillance, which convened an emergency conference on November 23, 2021. Another 100 sequences from Gauteng were randomly chosen and produced the same pattern [5].

THE HEAVILY MUTATEDOMICRON VARIANT

The full-length trimer, the S1 subunit, the NTD, and the receptor-binding domain (RBD) are Omicron spike proteins that latch on to receptors on human cells and are the principal focus of human immune responses.

The Omicron virus contains more than 50 mutations, with 26-35 amino acids distinct from the original SARS-CoV-2 virus or the Delta in its spike protein. S gene dropout or S gene target failure (SGTF) occurs when one of the three target genes encoding for the spike protein is not identified in the three-target RT-PCR experiment. The Omicron's complete genome is then sequenced using SGTF samples in table1. [6, 7]

Table 1: Characteristics of the Omicron Variant.

CHARACTERISTICS	OMICRON(B.1.1.529)
Country first found	South Africa
Time first reported	November 24, 2021
Mutation residues	43
Transmissibility	3-6 fold
Morbidity	Mild
Age of patients	Middle aged people
Vaccine effect	33%

USE OF BOOSTERS TO IMPROVE PROTECTION AGAINST THEOMICRON VARIANT

According to preliminary findings from teams in South Africa, Germany, Sweden, and the Pfizer-BioNtech cooperation, existing COVID-19 vaccination protection will not be completely lost. The boosters should improve Omicron resistance [8].

Third doses supercharge neutralizing-antibody levels, and this will likely provide a safeguard against the Omicron's ability to evade the antibodies. Bieniasz and colleagues reported that patients recovered from SARS-CoV-2 infection had antibodies to block the mutant spike, indicating that people with repeated exposure to Omicron's spike protein might have neutralizing activity against the Omicron.

The severity of the condition is a major worry. The Omicron VOC looks to be as mild as other corona virus strains, if not milder than Delta¹. According to preliminary findings, the Omicron form has a greater risk of reinfection than other variants. Most breakthrough infections with the Omicron have less severe symptoms than prior versions, yet hospitalization rates are rising. [9].

The Omicron virus contains more than 50 mutations, with 26-35 amino acids distinct from the original SARS-CoV-2 virus or the Delta in its spike protein. S gene dropout or S gene target failure (SGTF) occurs when one of the three target genes encoding for the spike protein is not identified in the three-target RT-PCR experiment. The number of people who need oxygen assistance was lower than in prior rounds. In the United States, one hospitalization and no deaths were documented among 43 Omicron cases with an initial follow-up. Cough, tiredness, and congestion or runny nose were the most often reported symptoms. The Omicron may be less harsh than its forerunners, but it's too soon to say whether it's truly more benign.[10].

Figure 3: Study of Spike Protein of Omicron and Antibody Interaction.**THE EFFECTIVE APPROACHES TO CONTROL THEOMICRON VARIANTS**

All variants of COVID-19 can cause severe disease or death, especially for the most vulnerable people, and thus prevention is always the key. The number of infections will depend on how much the variant escapes protection from vaccines, and how effective booster shots are at bolstering immunity, unfortunately, both of which remain unclear, the vaccines alone are not strong enough to control the pandemic [12]. Therefore, the most effective approaches are to isolate the infected people, wear a proper mask, keep a physical distance of at least 1 meter from others, keep hands clean, open windows to improve ventilation, avoid poorly ventilated or crowded spaces, cough or sneeze into a bent elbow or tissue and get vaccinated especially for vulnerable groups such as health workers and elderly [11, 12].

The pooled data from 16 randomized controlled trials, including 16236 COVID-19 patients treated with convalescent plasma showed that convalescent plasma has no benefit in non-severe patients, hence WHO recommends against using convalescent plasma to treat COVID-19 [13].

MOLECULAR DOCKING

Molecular docking is a technique of virtual simulation which is used to model the interaction between a small molecule and a protein at the atomic level. This technique is also used to characterize the behavior of the small molecules in the binding site of target protein.

Molecular docking is a computational technique to study the interaction between a target receptor and ligand at the molecular level and allows ranking of the legends by assessing their binding affinity towards the receptor using various scoring functions.

The docking process involves two basic steps -prediction of the ligand conformation and 2nd is binding of ligand within a target active site with accuracy that's why it technique is commonly used in structure-based drug design (SBDD). To study the molecular phenomena such as ligand binding pose and intermolecular interaction this method is applied for stability of a complex [14].

Figure 4: Molecular Docking**Table 2: Molecular Docking Tools for Protein-Ligand Interaction Studies.**

Tools	Key features	Reference
Auto-Dock	The methods available for conformational searching in Auto Dock are Lamarckian genetic algorithm, simulated annealing search, and a traditional genetic algorithm search. The prediction of binding free energies of small molecules to protein targets is based on a semi-empirical free energy force field.	[15]
GOLD	GOLD (genetic optimization for ligand docking) is an automated ligand docking program that allows full ligand conformational flexibility with partial flexibility of the protein and explores the binding conformations using a genetic algorithm.	[16]
DOCK6	DOCK 6 is a docking program that evaluates the conformational sampling of small molecules based on the anchor and grow search algorithm.	[17]
Swiss Dock	Swiss Dock is a web server that allows the docking of small molecules to target proteins that are based on the EADock DSS engine.	[18]

THEORY OF MOLECULAR DOCKING

- The theory of molecular docking is based on enzyme-substrate recognition process.
- In 1890, Emil Fischer proposed a model called 'lock and key model' that explained how biological system functions.

- Fischer explained the process of docking as LOCK AND KEY approach, in which one wants to determine correct orientation of key (ligand) which will open up the lock (protein).
- A substrate fits into active site of a macromolecule, just like a key fits into a lock.
- In 1958, Daniel Koshland proposed the 'Induced fit theory'.
- According to this theory, both ligand and receptor mutually adapt to each other through small conformational states, until best fit is achieved.
- In addition to small induced fit conformations, it has been seen that proteins can undergo large conformational changes. The plasticity of proteins allows it to switch from one state to another.[19,20]

TYPES OF MOLECULAR DOCKING

There are basically two types of molecular docking

1. Rigid docking
2. Flexible docking

RIGID DOCKING:

In rigid docking, the internal geometry of both ligand and receptor are treated as RIGID. The drawback of rigid docking is to neglect the conformational degrees of freedom of ligands. It fails to give satisfactory answer for flexible ligands will form different conformations.

FLEXIBLE DOCKING:

In this, both ligand and receptor are treated as FLEXIBLE BODIES. It is based on INDUCED FIT approach. It states that active site of protein undergoes continual replacement and the ligand interacts with it. [21]

APPLICATION OF MOLECULAR DOCKING

- It is used to screening for the side effects that can be caused by the interactions with other proteins, like proteases, Cytochrome P450 and others can be done.
- It is also possible to check the specificity of the potential drug against homologous proteins through docking.
- Docking is also a widely used tool in predicting protein-protein interactions.
- Knowledge of the molecular associations aids in understanding a variety of pathways taking place in the living and in revealing of the possible pharmacological targets.
- Docking combined with a scoring function can be used to quickly screen large databases of potential drugs in silico to identify molecules that are likely to bind to protein target of interest.[22]

METHODOLOGY

Steps of Molecular Docking:

Step 1 Protein structure preparation:

The second RBD of SARS-CoV-2 Omicron Variant in complexed with RBD-ACE2 (PDB ID – 7WPC) were retrieved from PDB site (<https://www.rcsb.org/structure/7WPC>) AutoDock Tools version 1.5.7 was used to generate the docking files. Using AutoDock Tools 1.5.7 all water molecules are removed, nonpolar hydrogen were merged, compute gasteiger and kollman charges were assigned and macromolecule saved in PDBQT file format. Grid box size of 60×60×60.

Step 2 Ligand structure preparation:

The structure was retrieved from PubChem (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) in SDF format. Structures followed by 2D cleaning, 3D optimization and viewing are done by using MarvinView.

Step 3 Molecular Docking:

Molecular docking study of various ligand against 7WPC was done using AutoDock 1.5.7 as molecular docking tool. Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm, with an initial population of 150 randomly placed individuals, a maximum number of 2,500,000 energy evaluations, a mutation rate of 0.02 and a crossover rate of 0.80 were used. AutoDock1.5.7 tools generated sixty possible binding conformations, i.e. sixty runs for each docking was done using genetic algorithm searches. Autogrid was used to obtain pre-calculated grid maps. [23,24, 25, 26]

Protein preparation for docking:

AutoDock expects that the input protein has polar hydrogens and that all water have been removed. You will get errors if this is not the case.

- a. Open file.pdb in ADT
File> Read Molecule
- b. Remove water Molecule
- c. Add polar hydrogens to target structure
Edit>Hydrogen>Add
Make sure that you select polar only
- d. Save the structure
File>Save>Write PDB

Ligand Initialization for docking

- e. Load the ligand file. The default file type in the file open dialogue is .pdbq. Change it to pdb.
Ligand >Input> open file
- f. Detect the root of the ligand.
Ligand >Torison Tree>Detect Root
- g. View rotatable bond
Ligand >Torison Tree>Choose Torsions
- h. Set rotatable bond (Active torsions) to 6 while allowing the fewest atoms to move.
Ligand>Torison Tree >Set number of Torsions
- i. Save the ligand
Ligand>output>save as PDBQ

Grid Map preparation:

Grid is placed on the target active site and should contain all atoms that could possibly interact with the ligand. It should be large enough to allow the ligand to fully rotate.

- j. Set target protein in which the ligand will dock.
Grid >Macromolecule> choose
- k. Set the Map Types that will be used for the grid.
Grid >Set Map Types>Choose Ligand
- l. Set the Grid Box position and size.
Grid Box...
For this exercise: Set each of the dimensions of the grid box to 60 points.
- m. Save the current grid positioning
File >Close Saving current
- n. Save Grid file
Grid>Output>Save GPF
In the file save dialog explicit type "Grid.gpf"

Docking parameter file Setup

- o. Set the protein target to be docked
Docking >Macromolecule>Set filename
Select the protein.pdbq file.
- p. Select the ligand to be docked
Docking>Ligand >Choose
- q. Set search parameters
Docking> Search Parameter >Genetic Algorithm
Make the following change to the parameter:
Number of runs >1
Maximum number of energy evaluations>1500000
- r. Set Docking parameters
Docking parameters...
- s. Set the Docking output parameter file
Docking >Output>Lamarckian GA
In the file save dialog explicit type "Dock.dpf"

Running AutoGrid and AutoDock

- t. Run AutoGrid4 in the command line
- u. Run AutoDock4 in the command line

Evaluation of Docking

- v. When AutoDock completed its run, you can view the results in AutoDock Tools.
Analyze>Docking>Open

Open the dock.dlg file.

w. Load macromolecule into view

Analyze> Macromolecule> Choose

x. View the conformations

Analyze> Conformations> Play [27-31]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 3: Drugs Used For Docking.

DRUG	IUPAC NAME	MOLECULAR FORMULA	MOLECULAR WEIGHT	STRUCTURE
Acyclovir	2-amino-9-(2-hydroxyethoxymethyl)-1H-purin-6-one	$C_8H_{11}N_5O_3$	225.2g/mol	
Ambroxol	4-[(2-amino-3,5-dibromophenyl)methylamino]cyclohexan-1-ol	$C_{13}H_{18}Br_2N_2O$	378.1g/mol	
Arbidol	ethyl 6-bromo-4-[(dimethylamino)methyl]-5-hydroxy-1-methyl-2-(phenylsulfanylmethyl)indole-3-carboxylate	$C_{22}H_{25}BrN_2O_3S$	477.4g/mol	 HCl
Atovaquone	3-[4-(4-chlorophenyl)cyclohexyl]-4-hydroxynaphthalene-1,2-dione	$C_{22}H_{19}ClO_3$	366.8g/mol	

Avermectin	(1'R,2R,3S,4'S,6S,8'R,10'E,12'S,13'S,14'E,16'E,20'R,21'R,24'S)-2-[(2S)-butan-2-yl]-21',24'-dihydroxy-12'-[(2R,4S,5S,6S)-5-[(2S,4S,5S,6S)-5-hydroxy-4-methoxy-6-methyloxan-2-yl]oxy-4-methoxy-6-methyloxan-2-yl]oxy-3,11',13',22'-tetramethylspiro[2,3-dihydropyran-6,6'-3,7,19-trioxatetracyclo[15.6.1.14,8.020,24]pentacosan-10,14,16,22-tetraene]-2'-one	$C_{48}H_{72}O_{14}$	873.1g/mol	
Azithromycin	(2R,3S,4R,5R,8R,10R,11R,12S,13S,14R)-11-[(2S,3R,4S,6R)-4-(dimethylamino)-3-hydroxy-6-methyloxan-2-yl]oxy-2-ethyl-3,4,10-trihydroxy-13-[(2R,4R,5S,6S)-5-hydroxy-4-methoxy-4,6-dimethyloxan-2-yl]oxy-3,5,6,8,10,12,14-heptamethyl-1-oxa-6-azacyclopentadecan-15-one	$C_{38}H_{72}N_2O_{12}$	749g/mol	
Baricitinib	2-[1-ethylsulfonyl-3-[4-(7H-pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-yl)pyrazol-1-yl]azetidin-3-yl]acetonitrile	$C_{16}H_{17}N_7O_2S$	371.4g/mol	
Brincidofovir	[(2S)-1-(4-amino-2-oxopyrimidin-1-yl)-3-hydroxypropan-2-yl]oxymethyl-(3-hexadecoxypropoxy)phosphinic acid	$C_{27}H_{52}N_3O_7P$	561.7g/mol	

Camostat	[4-[2-[2-(dimethylamino)-2-oxoethoxy]-2-oxoethyl]phenyl] 4-(diaminomethylideneamino)benzoate	$C_{20}H_{22}N_4O_5$	398.4g/mol	
Cenicriviroc	(5E)-8-[4-(2-butoxyethoxy)phenyl]-1-(2-methylpropyl)-N-[4-[(S)-(3-propylimidazol-4-yl)methylsulfinyl]phenyl]-3,4-dihydro-2H-1-benzazocine-5-carboxamide	$C_{41}H_{52}N_4O_4S$	696.9g/mol	
Chebularic acid	2-[13,14,15,18,19,20,31,35,36-nonahydroxy-2,10,23,28,32-pentaoxo-5-(3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoyl)oxy-3,6,9,24,27,33-hexaoxaheptacyclo[28.7.1.04,25.07,26.011,16.017,22.034,38]octatriaconta-1(37),11,13,15,17,19,21,34(38),35-nonaen-29-yl]acetic acid	$C_{41}H_{30}O_{27}$	954.7g/mol	
Chloroquine	4-N-(7-chloroquinolin-4-yl)-1-N,1-N-diethylpentane-1,4-diamine	$C_{18}H_{26}ClN_3$	319.9g/mol	
Cicesonide	[2-[(1S,2S,4R,6R,8S,9S,11S,12S,13R)-6-cyclohexyl-11-hydroxy-9,13-dimethyl-16-oxo-5,7-dioxapentacyclo[10.8.0.02,9.04,8.013,18]jicosa-14,17-dien-8-yl]-2-oxoethyl] 2-methylpropanoate	$C_{32}H_{44}O_7$	540.7g/mol	

Ciclesonide	[2-(1S,2S,4R,6R,8S,9S,11S,12S,13R)-6-cyclohexyl-11-hydroxy-9,13-dimethyl-16-oxo-5,7-dioxapentacyclo[10.8.0.02,9.04,8.013,18]icosa-14,17-dien-8-yl]-2-oxoethyl] 2-methylpropanoate	$C_{32}H_{44}O_7$	540.7g/mol	
Clarithromycin	(3R,4S,5S,6R,7R,9R,11R,12R,13S,14R)-6-[(2S,3R,4S,6R)-4-(dimethylamino)-3-hydroxy-6-methoxyan-2-yl]oxy-14-ethyl-12,13-dihydroxy-4-[(2R,4R,5S,6S)-5-hydroxy-4-methoxy-4,6-dimethoxyan-2-yl]oxy-7-methoxy-3,5,7,9,11,13-hexamethyl-oxacyclotetradecane-2,10-dione	$C_{38}H_{69}NO_{13}$	748g/mol	
Dihydroergotamine	(6aR,9R,10aR)-N-[(1S,2S,4R,7S)-7-benzyl-2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5,8-dioxo-3-oxa-6,9-diazatricyclo[7.3.0.02,6]dodecan-4-yl]-7-methyl-6,6a,8,9,10,10a-hexahydro-4H-indolo[4,3-fg]quinoline-9-carboxamide	$C_{33}H_{37}N_5O_5$	583.7g/mol	
Doxycycline	(4S,4aR,5S,5aR,6R,12aR)-4-(dimethylamino)-1,5,10,11,12a-pentahydroxy-6-methyl-3,12-dioxo-4a,5,5a,6-tetrahydro-4H-tetracene-2-carboxamide	$C_{22}H_{24}N_2O_8$	444.4g/mol	

Efavirenz	(4S)-6-chloro-4-(2-cyclopropylethynyl)-4-(trifluoromethyl)-1H-3,1-benzoxazin-2-one	$C_{14}H_9ClF_3NO_2$	315.67g/mol	
Emtricitabine	4-amino-5-fluoro-1-[(2R,5S)-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-oxathiolan-5-yl]pyrimidin-2-one	$C_8H_{10}FN_3O_3S$	247.25g/mol	
Ergotamine	(6aR,9R)-N-[(1S,2S,4R,7S)-7-benzyl-2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5,8-dioxo-3-oxa-6,9-diazatricyclo[7.3.0.0.2,6]dodecan-4-yl]-7-methyl-6,6a,8,9-tetrahydro-4H-indolo[4,3-fg]quinoline-9-carboxamide	$C_{33}H_{35}N_5O_5$	581.7g/mol	
Favipravir	5-fluoro-2-oxo-1H-pyrazine-3-carboxamide	$C_5H_4FN_3O_2$	157.1g/mol	
Fingolimod	2-amino-2-[2-(4-octylphenyl)ethyl]propane-1,3-diol	$C_{19}H_{33}NO_2$	307.5g/mol	
Fluconazole	2-(2,4-difluorophenyl)-1,3-bis(1,2,4-triazol-1-yl)propan-2-ol	$C_{13}H_{12}F_2N_6O$	306.27g/mol	
Fluvoxamine	2-[(E)-[5-methoxy-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)pentylidene]amino]oxyethanamine	$C_{15}H_{21}F_3N_2O_2$	318.33g/mol	

Ganciclovir	2-amino-9-(1,3-dihydroxypropan-2-ylloxymethyl)-1H-purin-6-one	$C_9H_{13}N_5O_4$	255.23g/mol	
Hydroxychloroquine	2-[4-[(7-chloroquinolin-4-yl)amino]pentyl-ethylamino]ethanol	$C_{18}H_{26}ClN_3O$	335.9g/mol	
Imatinib	methanesulfonic acid;4-[(4-methylpiperazin-1-yl)methyl]-N-[4-methyl-3-[(4-pyridin-3-yl)pyrimidin-2-yl]amino]phenyl]benzamide	$C_{30}H_{35}N_7O_4S$	589.7g/mol	
Ivermectine	(1R,5'S,6R,6'R,8R,10E,12S,13S,14E,16E,20R,21R,24S)-21,24-dihydroxy-12-[(2R,4S,5S,6S)-5-[(4S,5S,6S)-5-hydroxy-4-methoxy-6-methyloxan-2-yl]oxy-4-methoxy-6-methyloxan-2-yl]oxy-5',11,13,22-tetramethyl-6'-propan-2-ylspiro[3,7,19-trioxatetracyclo[15.6.1.14,8.0.20,24]pentacos-10,14,16,22-tetraene-6,2'-oxane]-2-one	$C_{95}H_{146}O_{28}$	1736.2g/mol	
Lamivudine	4-amino-1-[(2R,5S)-2-(hydroxymethyl)-1,3-oxathiolan-5-yl]pyrimidin-2-one	$C_8H_{11}N_3O_3S$	229.26g/mol	

Lopinivir	(2S)-N-[(2S,4S,5S)-5-[[2-(2,6-dimethylphenoxy)acetyl]amino]-4-hydroxy-1,6-diphenylhexan-2-yl]-3-methyl-2-(2-oxo-1,3-diazinan-1-yl)butanamide	$C_{37}H_{48}N_4O_5$	628.8g/mol	
Methylethionine	(6aR,9R)-N-[(2S)-1-hydroxybutan-2-yl]-7-methyl-6,6a,8,9-tetrahydro-4H-indolo[4,3-fg]quinoline-9-carboxamide	$C_{20}H_{25}N_3O_2$	339.4g/mol	
Molnupiravir	((2R,3S,4R,5R)-3,4-Dihydroxy-5-((E)-4-(hydroxyimino)-2-oxo-3,4-dihydropyrimidin-1(2H)-yl)tetrahydrofuran-2-yl)methyl isobutyrate	$C_{13}H_{19}N_3O_7$	329.31 g/mol	
Nafomostat	(6-carbamimidoylnaphthalen-2-yl) 4-(diaminomethylideneamino)benzoate	$C_{19}H_{17}N_5O_2$	347.4g/mol	
Nermatrelvir	(1R,2S,5S)-N-[(1S)-1-cyano-2-[(3S)-2-oxopyrrolidin-3-yl]ethyl]-3-[(2S)-3,3-dimethyl-2-[(2,2,2-trifluoroacetyl)amino]butanoyl]-6,6-dimethyl-3-azabicyclo[3.1.0]hexane-2-carboxamide	$C_{23}H_{32}F_3N_5O_4$	499.5g/mol	
Nevirapine	2-cyclopropyl-7-methyl-2,4,9,15-tetrazatricyclo[9.4.0.0.3,8]pentadecan-1(11),3,5,7,12,14-hexaen-10-one	$C_{15}H_{14}N_4O$	266.3g/mol	

Noscapine	(3S)-6,7-dimethoxy-3-[(5R)-4-methoxy-6-methyl-7,8-dihydro-5H-[1,3]dioxolo[4,5-g]isoquinolin-5-yl]-3H-2-benzofuran-1-one	$C_{22}H_{23}NO_7$	413.4g/mol	
Oseltamivir	ethyl (3R,4R,5S)-4-acetamido-5-amino-3-pentan-3-yloxycyclohexene-1-carboxylate	$C_{16}H_{28}N_2O_4$	312.4g/mol	
Otamixaban	methyl (2R,3R)-2-[(3-carbamimidoylphenyl)methyl]-3-[[4-(1-oxidopyridin-1-ium-4-yl)benzoyl]amino]butanoate	$C_{25}H_{26}N_4O_4$	446.5g/mol	
Paracetamol	N-(4-hydroxyphenyl)acetamide	$C_8H_9NO_2$	151.16g/mol	
Peniciclovir	2-amino-9-[4-hydroxy-3-(hydroxymethyl)butyl]-1H-purin-6-one	$C_{10}H_{15}N_5O_3$	253.26g/mol	
Puerarin	7-hydroxy-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-8-[(2S,3R,4R,5S,6R)-3,4,5-trihydroxy-6-(hydroxymethyl)oxan-2-yl]chromen-4-one	$C_{21}H_{20}O_9$	416.4g/mol	
Remdesivir	2-ethylbutyl [(2S)-2-[[[(2R,3S,4R,5R)-5-(4-aminopyrrolo[2,1-f][1,2,4]triazin-7-yl)-5-cyano-3,4-dihydroxyoxolan-2-yl]methoxyphenoxyphosphoryl]amino]propanoate	$C_{27}H_{35}N_6O_8P$	602.6g/mol	

Ribavirin	1-[(2R,3R,4S,5R)-3,4-dihydroxy-5-(hydroxymethyl)oxolan-2-yl]-1,2,4-triazole-3-carboxamide	$C_8H_{12}N_4O_5$	244.2g/mol	
Ruloxitinib	(3R)-3-cyclopentyl-3-[4-(7H-pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-yl)pyrazol-1-yl]propanenitrile	$C_{17}H_{18}N_6$	306.4g/mol	
Selinexor	(Z)-3-[3-[3,5-bis(trifluoromethyl)phenyl]-1,2,4-triazol-1-yl]-N'-pyrazin-2-ylprop-2-enehydrazide	$C_{17}H_{11}F_6N_7O$	443.3g/mol	
Streptomycin	2-[(1R,2R,3S,4R,5R,6S)-3-(diaminomethylideneamino)-4-[(2R,3R,4R,5S)-3-[(2S,3S,4S,5R,6S)-4,5-dihydroxy-6-(hydroxymethyl)-3-(methylamino)oxan-2-yl]oxy-4-formyl-4-hydroxy-5-methyloxolan-2-yl]oxy-2,5,6-trihydroxycyclohexyl]guanidine	$C_{21}H_{39}N_7O_{12}$	581.6g/mol	
Tenofovir	[(2R)-1-(6-aminopurin-9-yl)propan-2-yl]oxymethylphosphonic acid	$C_9H_{14}N_5O_4P$	287.21g/mol	
Tofacitinib	3-[(3R,4R)-4-methyl-3-[methyl(7H-pyrrolo[2,3-d]pyrimidin-4-yl)amino]piperidin-1-yl]-3-oxopropanenitrile	$C_{16}H_{20}N_6O$	312.37g/mol	

Valaciclovir	2-[(2-amino-6-oxo-1H-purin-9-yl)methoxy]ethyl (2S)-2-amino-3-methylbutanoate	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄	324.34g/mol	
Zidovudin	1-[(2R,4S,5S)-4-azido-5-(hydroxymethyl)oxolan-2-yl]-5-methylpyrimidine-2,4-dione	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄	267.24g/mol	

DOCKING RESULTS

Table 4: Drugs Used For Molecular Docking.

Drug	Estimated Free Energy of Binding	Estimated loss of torsional energy upon binding	Estimated of free energy upon binding	Estimated Inhibition Constant, Ki	Electrostatic Energy	Final Internal Energy	Total Docking Energy	
Aciclovir	-2.58 kcal/mol	+1.7898 kcal/mol		12.78uM	+0.55 kcal/mol	-1.81 kcal/mol		
Ambroxol	-4.82 kcal/mol	+1.4915 kcal/mol		291.51uM	-0.01 kcal/mol	-0.38 kcal/mol		
Arbidol	-3.91 kcal/mol	+2.6847 kcal/mol		1.37mM	+0.23 kcal/mol	-2.81 kcal/mol		

Atovaquone	-6.46 kcal/mol	+0.8949 kcal/mol	21.69uM	-0.14 kcal/mol	-0.76 kcal/mol	
Avermectine	-6.25 kcal/mol	+2.9830 kcal/mol	26.41uM	+0.04 kcal/mol	-3.50 kcal/mol	
Azithromycin	-3.65 kcal/mol	+3.5796 kcal/mol	490.55uM	+0.40 kcal/mol	-5.39 kcal/mol	
Baricitinib	-6.46 kcal/mol	+1.7898 kcal/mol	18.54 uM	-0.14 kcal/mol	-0.92 kcal/mol	
Brincidovir	+1.82 kcal/mol	+8.6507 kcal/mol	NA	-0.15 kcal/mol	-6.14 kcal/mol	

Camostat	-4.05 kcal/mol	+2.6847 kcal/mol	1.07nM	+0.10 kcal/mol	-4.04 kcal/mol	
Cenicriviroc	-4.96 kcal/mol	+5.0711 kcal/mol	15.55uM	-0.03 kcal/mol	-3.95 kcal/mol	
Chebulagic acid	-5.55 kcal/mol	+5.3694 kcal/mol	271.68uM	-0.78 kcal/mol	-9.73 kcal/mol	
Chloroquine	-4.36 kcal/mol	+2.3864 kcal/mol	636.14uM	-0.07 kcal/mol	-1.32 kcal/mol	
Ciclesonide	-4.23 kcal/mol	+2.0881 kcal/mol	4.41uM	+0.03 kcal/mol	-2.19 kcal/mol	

Ciclesonid	-3.93 kcal/mol	+2.0881 kcal/mol	51.42nM	+0.00 kcal/mol	-2.62 kcal/mol	
Clarithromycin	-7.26 kcal/mol	+3.5796 kcal/mol	4.77uM	-0.04 kcal/mol	-5.50 kcal/mol	
Dihydroergotamine	-11.93 kcal/mol	+1.4915 kcal/mol	1.80nM	+0.00 kcal/mol	-3.98 kcal/mol	
Doxycycline	-5.51 kcal/mol	+2.0881 kcal/mol	91.89uM	-0.25 kcal/mol	-4.89 kcal/mol	
Efavirenz	-4.29 kcal/mol	+0.8949 kcal/mol	245.85uM	-0.06 kcal/mol	-0.61 kcal/mol	

Emtricitabine	-4.02 kcal/mol	+1.1932 kcal/mol	1.14mM	-0.23 kcal/mol	-1.77 kcal/mol	
Ergotamine	-11.49 kcal/mol	+1.4915 kcal/mol	3.80nM	+0.00 kcal/mol	-4.59 kcal/mol	
Favipiravir	-4.05 kcal/mol	+0.2983 kcal/mol	1.36mM	-0.29 kcal/mol	-0.30 kcal/mol	
Fingolimod	-3.97 kcal/mol	+4.475 kcal/mol	259.78uM	+0.00 kcal/mol	-4.41 kcal/mol	
Fluconazole	-3.78 kcal/mol	+1.7898 kcal/mol	1.47nM	-0.11 kcal/mol	-1.72 kcal/mol	

Fluvoxamine	-0.56 kcal/mol	+3.2813 kcal/mol	390.00mM	+0.25 kcal/mol	-4.52 kcal/mol	
Ganiciclovir	-6.55 kcal/mol	+2.0881 kcal/mol	15.79uM	+0.00 kcal/mol	-4.95 kcal/mol	
Hydroxychloroquine	-4.01 kcal/mol	+2.9830 kcal/mol	2.13uM	-0.15 kcal/mol	-1.87 kcal/mol	
Imatinib	-3.65 kcal/mol	+2.0881 kcal/mol	239.29uM	+1.50 kcal/mol	-1.14 kcal/mol	
Ivermectine	-5.45 kcal/mol	+3.2813 kcal/mol	100.63uM	+0.02 kcal/mol	-2.71 kcal/mol	

Lamivudine	-4.04 kcal/mol	+1.1932 kcal/mol	1.10mM	-0.22 kcal/mol	-1.70 kcal/mol	
Lopinivir	-4.01 kcal/mol	+4.7728 kcal/mol	131.74uM	-008 kcal/mol	-5.62 kcal/mol	
Methylergonovine	-7.96 kcal/mol	+1.4915 kcal/mol	1.47uM	+0.00 kcal/mol	-0.98 kcal/mol	
Molnupiravir	-4.23 kcal/mol	+2.6847 kcal/mol	796.77uM	-0.27 kcal/mol	-2.49 kcal/mol	
Nermatrelvir	-5.55 kcal/mol	+2.6847 kcal/mol	84.57uM	+0.00 kcal/mol	-3.49 kcal/mol	

Nevirapine	-5.42 kcal/mol	+0.2983 kcal/mol	106.51uM	-0.04 kcal/mol	-0.32 kcal/mol	
Nofamostat	-8.53 kcal/mol	+1.4915 kcal/mol	557.64uM	+0.00 kcal/mol	-1.89 kcal/mol	
Noscapine	-4.96 kcal/mol	+1.1932 kcal/mol	231.15uM	-0.08 kcal/mol	-1.67 kcal/mol	
Oseltamivir	-4.66 kcal/mol	+2.3864 kcal/mol	1.46mM	-1.07 kcal/mol	-2.38 kcal/mol	
Otamixaban	-5.47 kcal/mol	+2.9830 kcal/mol	98.15uM	-0.01 kcal/mol	-1.48 kcal/mol	

Paracetamol	-4.27 kcal/mol	+0.5966 kcal/mol	738.56uM	-0.23 kcal/mol	-0.18 kcal/mol	
Peniciclovir	-4.36 kcal/mol	+2.3864 kcal/mol	3.76mM	+0.46 kcal/mol	-1.12 kcal/mol	
Puerarin	-3.93 kcal/mol	+2.6847 kcal/mol	1.33uM	-0.17 kcal/mol	-4.57 kcal/mol	
Remdesivir	-4.66 kcal/mol	+5.0711 kcal/mol	382.57uM	-0.09 kcal/mol	-5.78 kcal/mol	
Ribavirin	-4.82 kcal/mol	+1.7898 kcal/mol	3.09mM	-0.13 kcal/mol	-3.52 kcal/mol	
Ruxolitinib	-3.28 kcal/mol	+1.1932 kcal/mol	14.65uM	-0.18 kcal/mol	-0.91 kcal/mol	

Selinexor	-4.48 kcal/mol	+2.0881 kcal/mol	536.57uM	-0.16 kcal/mol	-2.95 kcal/mol	
Streptomycin	-2.58 kcal/mol	+4.7728 kcal/mol	357.48uM	+0.00 kcal/mol	-10.40 kcal/mol	
Tenofovir	-3.31 kcal/mol	+2.3864 kcal/mol	3.76mM	-0.83 kcal/mol	-2.83 kcal/mol	
Tofacitinib	-3.91 kcal/mol	+0.8949 kcal/mol	16.38uM	-0.35 kcal/mol	-0.34 kcal/mol	
Valaciclovir	-3.28 kcal/mol	+2.6847 kcal/mol	55.58uM	+0.00 kcal/mol	-3.33 kcal/mol	

Zidovudine	-5.05	+1.1932	198.80uM	+0.00	-1.25
	kcal/mol	kcal/mol		kcal/mol	kcal/mol

CONCLUSION

On Nov 25, 2021, about 23 months since the first reported case of COVID-19 and after a global estimated 260 million cases and 5.2 million deaths, a new SARS-CoV-2 variant of concern (VoC), omicron, was reported. Molecular docking is a computational technique to study the interaction between a target receptor and ligand at the molecular level and allows ranking of the legends by assessing their binding affinity towards the receptor using various scoring functions. Docking may be used to virtually screen vast libraries of compounds, rate the findings, and provide structural hypotheses about how the ligands block the target, which is extremely useful in lead optimization. AutoDock is an automated tool that predicts ligand interactions. Because of its 2.57Å resolution, the 7WPC SARS-CoV-2 omicron variant is chosen as a protein. Molecular docking of the omicron version with 50 antimicrobial medicines was carried out utilising AutoDock tools. The top five medications, based on their binding energy, were chosen from a pool of 50 drugs as follows Dihydroergotamine (-11.93 kcal/mol), Ergotamine (-11.49 kcal/mol), Nofamostat (-8.53 kcal/mol), Methylergonovine (-7.96 kcal/mol), Clarithromycin (-7.26 kcal/mol).

GRAPH.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We are immensely thankful to Dr. Dinesh Kaushik for their constant encouragement and support providing during the study.

ABBREVIATION

VOC: Variant of Concern;

Vs: Versus;

SBDD: Structure Based Drug Design.

Pvt Ltd.: Private limited;

PCR: Polymerase Chain Reaction;
RBD: Receptor Binding Domain.

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